

Creating atmospheres: the effects of ambient scent and coloured lighting on environmental assessment

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Abstract

Environments stimulate multiple sensory modalities at a time. However, little knowledge exists into how these stimuli combine to affect an individual's experience of an environment. In today's experience oriented society (Pine & Gilmore, 1999), coloured lighting and ambient scents are considered to be trendy atmosphere creators. Ambient scent as well as coloured light appears to have only modest effects on mood, but each has the potential to affect environmental assessment. The focus of this study was to explore whether these factors, when combined, strengthen or hamper each other in creating a more positive experience. Based on the results of a pre-test, two scents and two coloured lighting ambiences were selected as experimental variables, to produce two congruent (in which fragrance and light colour match) and two incongruent (in which fragrance and light colour do not match) conditions. An experimental evaluation with 90 users showed that coloured lighting and scent positively affect the assessment of a room, while there were no effects found for congruency. More significant effects were found for coloured lighting than for scent. This study also demonstrated that coloured lighting and ambient scent can be used to alter impressions of the arousal and pleasure that is attributed to places. Apart from these results, the study proved to be valuable for gaining insight into the methodology for evaluating atmospheres created by ambient scents.

Key words

Atmosphere creation, ambient scent, coloured lighting, user experience, environmental assessment

Introduction

Scents constitute an important source of information for people during their daily routines. For example, scents are said to influence people's product choice (Byrne-Quinn, 1991), the time they spend in a shop (Bone & Ellen, 1999) and the impression they form of others (Baron, 1991). However, several practical problems arise in studying scents, such as the variability between subjects in their sensitivity and their liking for certain scents, scent neutralization and maintaining a constant scent concentration. These problems might have well played a part in the fact that fragrances are not commonly used as behavioural modifiers in commercial environments.

In addition to fragrance, lighting can also greatly affect our daily lives. For example, lighting has been found to influence well-being (Flynn, 1992), performance (Knez, 1995), depression and stress (McCull & Veitch, 2001). Unfortunately the combined effects of fragrance and lighting on environmental assessments have not been studied to date and theory is still lacking to be able to predict specific behavioural and/or affective effects of fragrance and lighting on people. Several studies have been conducted that focused primarily on the effects of scent in the retailing branch. The results from these studies demonstrate modest effects of scents on mood. For example, in her meta study Dalton (2002) reports little evidence of the effectiveness of either pleasant or unpleasant odours to modulate mood or worker's performance. The same appears to apply for lighting. In their review, McCull and Veitch (2001) conclude that in general the evidence does not show dramatic effects of fluorescent lamp type on arousal, stress, performance and depression.

The effects of fragrance and lighting on environmental assessment

In contrast to the modest effects on mood, several studies did demonstrate the effects of ambient scent and lighting on environmental assessment. Spangenberg, Crowley and Henderson (1996) studied the effects of scents in a store environment. They found that evaluations of the overall store, of the store environment and of the merchandise were more positive when the store was scented than when it was not scented. Little difference was found among evaluations of the store when it was scented with affectively pleasing scents versus affectively neutral scents (these scents are neither experienced as pleasant, nor as unpleasant). The authors therefore conclude that the specific scent used did not matter as much as the presence of a scent.

In a comparison of otherwise identical rooms by Clifford (1985), subjects indicated that the room containing a low level of fragrance was brighter, cleaner and fresher (while none of the subjects noted the scents). Hellema (1994) found similar results in a study, in which subjects indicated that a scented room was perceived as larger than an unscented one. Vroon (1989) even claims that it is possible to have an ugly interior judged as tasteful by adding a pleasant odour

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Apart from studying the effect of the mere presence of fragrances on people's assessment of the environment, other researchers have made a distinction between the effects of congruent (i.e. fitting the setting) and incongruent (i.e. not fitting the setting) scents. Some odours, although generally perceived as pleasant, may be viewed as inappropriate in a particular context (Bone & Ellen, 1999), which might affect people's judgments.

Schifferstein and Blok (2002) studied the effects of congruent and incongruent ambient scents in a retail store. They found that the presence of a pleasant ambient scent did not affect sales in general. In addition, ambient scent did not increase sales for a thematically congruent product, nor did it decrease sales for a thematically incongruent product. However, measuring sales might not have been the most appropriate dependent measurement to study the effect of ambient scent, since other studies have demonstrated that scents have little direct effects on consumers' spending (Chebat & Michon, 2003).

Mattila and Wirtz (2001) studied the effects of congruency of two stimuli, music and scent, on consumer experience (pleasure, approach, perceived store environment, impulse buying and satisfaction). However, in contrast to the study of Schifferstein and Blok, Mattila and Wirtz focused on congruency in arousal (slow tempo music with relaxing scent and fast beat music with arousing scent) instead of in semantics (thematic congruence of stimuli). The findings support the belief that when stimuli in the environment act together to provide a coherent atmosphere, the individual in the environment will react more positively (that is for approach behaviours, impulse buying and satisfaction). Still, a mismatch between the stimuli seemed to provide more pleasure than no stimuli at all. However, the authors note that beauty is in the eye of the beholder and similarly, the appropriateness of the stimuli. Also the novelty can wear off quickly, which might reduce pleasure after a while.

In conclusion, it seems that scents can positively influence environmental assessments (of store environments). It does not seem to matter whether the scents fit the environment semantically, as long as the scent matches other stimuli in the environment in terms of the level of arousal.

Most studies investigating the effects of lighting on environmental assessment, focused on the effects of white lighting. In his study, Flynn (1992) examined how the location and illuminance of white light can affect people's impressions of a room. It was found that low-level overhead lighting makes a space feel confined. Low lighting levels in the region of the occupant and higher levels in the peripheral area reinforced privacy. Pleasantness seemed to be enhanced by a moderate illuminance level with non-uniform wall lighting.

Investigating the effects of coloured lighting, Mikellides (1996) found consistent evidence for the notion that red light or red paint induced visual warmth in comparison to blue but only on the cognitive level, not on the physiological level. Thus there is the suggestion of warmth in response to red.

Although a respectable amount of research has been performed on the effects of colours, apart from the study of Mikellides (1996) no other studies were found that focused on the effects of coloured *lighting* on environmental assessment.

The current study was aimed to elucidate the independent effects of ambient scent and coloured lighting on the user experience and environmental assessment. In addition, the potential interaction effects between coloured light and scent were investigated, both in congruent and incongruent atmospheres.

Method

Design

Two independent variables, scent and lighting colour, were manipulated independently on 3 levels, resulting in a 3 (Scent: neutral vs. refreshing vs. relaxing) x 3 (Lighting colour: neutral vs. refreshing vs. relaxing) design. This design also resulted in 2 congruent and 2 incongruent combinations of scent and colour, as indicated in Table 1. Scents were tested between subjects, meaning that each participant evaluated only one scent condition. Coloured lighting was tested within subjects, meaning that each participant evaluated all lighting conditions. Thus, participants were assigned to one scent condition and successively experienced all three

lighting conditions within that scent condition. Testing scents within subjects would involve a time-consuming process of ventilating the room to remove the scents after each measurement. Another disadvantage of a fully within subjects design is that participants would experience the same coloured light settings three times (in each scent condition). This could lead to boredom or even annoyance. Also the participants might become aware of the scent manipulation, of which they were deliberately not told.

Table 1, Conditions in main experiment

<i>Lighting</i>	<i>Scent</i>	Neutral	Refreshing scent: citrus	Relaxing scent: musky
Neutral				
Refreshing lighting: yellow			Congruent	Incongruent
Relaxing lighting: violet			Incongruent	Congruent

Participants

Ninety subjects between 18-60 years old participated in the study (46 male; 44 female). The average age was 35.

Environmental setting

The experiment was performed in the HomeLab at the Philips Research laboratories in Eindhoven, the Netherlands. HomeLab is a future home-simulation, a test laboratory that looks like a normal house and thus provides us with a relatively natural context in which to test the assessments of the participants. The experiment was conducted in the master bedroom, which provided a quasi-naturalistic setting, representing a hotel room scenario.

Manipulations

During a pre-test 20 participants (10 male; 10 female) were asked to rate 4 fragrances and 5 coloured lighting settings (red, orange, yellow, violet and blue-green) by means of a 7-point Likert scale, determining subjective intensity, pleasure and stimulating / relaxing association. Based on the results, two scents (one refreshing and one relaxing) and two coloured lighting ambiances (one refreshing and one relaxing) were selected as independent variables. These stimuli differed only in terms of relaxing and stimulating association, but were perceived as equally pleasant and intense, which was essential to avoid bias in the results of the main experiment. For the refreshing condition a citrus scent and the yellow coloured lighting were

selected, whereas for the relaxing condition a musky scent (consisting of a mix of, among others, lavender and cinnamon) with the violet coloured lighting were selected.

Measurements

During the main experiment the user assessment of the environment was investigated by measuring the subjective affective reaction and evaluation of the environment. This was done by means of three questionnaires. One questionnaire measured the participants' internal affective state and consisted of the "Scales of the affective quality attributed to places" by Russell and Pratt (1981), measuring pleasure and arousal, on a scale ranging from 1=very inaccurate to 7=very accurate. The other two sub-questionnaires measured the evaluation of the environment. The scale of Bell, Holbrook and Solomon (1991) measured perceived unity, aesthetic response, social impression, general liking and intention to own on a scale from 1=very high to 7=very low. The scale of Flynn, Hendrick, Spencer and Martyniuk (1979) measured evaluative response, perceptual clarity and spaciousness on a scale from 1=very high to 7=very low. In addition, questions were added to measure innovativity, comfortable temperature, tidiness and feeling comfortable, also measured on a scale ranging from 1=very high to 7=very low.

Procedure

Each lighting condition (atmosphere) was experienced for 15 minutes. During that time the participants filled in the questionnaires. The order of the lighting and scent conditions were balanced to avoid order effects and bias caused by time of the day. Participants were not told about the presence of the fragrances or coloured lighting before or during the experiment to avoid demand bias.

Results

Before testing the hypotheses, factor analyses and scale analyses were performed to construct robust and meaningful dependent variables. Subsequently, the data were analysed employing repeated measures analysis of variance (REMANOVA).

Scale construction

After recoding, the 10 items measuring experienced arousal in the room (Russell & Pratt, 1981) were combined into one variable by computing the mean for each experimental group (all Cronbach's alphas of the experimental groups were $>.8$), and labelled "arousal". Similarly the 10 items measuring valence were combined into one variable labelled "pleasantness" (all Cronbach's alphas $>.9$).

Principal Component Analyses (PCA) were performed on the items from the scales of Bell, Holbrook and Solomon (1991) and Flynn, Hendrick, Spencer and Martyniuk (1979).

Subsequently, two variables were constructed:

- Evaluation (consisting of the items measuring aesthetic response, social impression, general liking, evaluative response, inviting impression, intention to own and feeling comfortable)
- Spaciousness (consisting of the items measuring spaciousness, innovativity, comfortable temperature and tidiness).

The internal consistencies of these scales were acceptable for all experimental groups, with Cronbach's alphas ranging between .94 and .97 for evaluation, and between .65 and .77 for spaciousness.

REMANOVAs of these four dependent variables are reported below. All analyses were performed employing the full model: 3 (lighting colour, within) x 3 (scent, between).

Assessment of arousal

The mean scores on arousal for each of the experimental groups and conditions are reported in Table 2. Both coloured lighting conditions resulted in higher scores than the white light condition, representing more arousal. This main effect was significant ($F(2,174)=18.44$, $p<.001$). Scores for the violet and yellow light did not differ significantly. There were no remaining significant effects.

Assessment of pleasantness

Again, the mean scores are reported in Table 2, with higher scores representing more pleasant assessments. Both coloured lighting conditions generated significantly higher scores ($F(2,174)=12.89$, $p<.001$) than the white lighting. Yellow was rated more pleasant than violet. The main effect of Scent was also significant ($F(2,87)=3.76$, $p=.027$), with both scented conditions generating more pleasant assessments than the neutral one. No significant interaction effect was found.

Table 2, Assessment of arousal, pleasantness, evaluation and spaciousness

	<i>Scent</i>	Citrus	Neutral	Musky	Total
	<i>Lighting</i>				
Arousal	Yellow	4.11	4.15	4.39	4.22 _a
	Neutral	3.16	3.28	3.41	3.28 _{a,b}
	Violet	4.06	3.93	3.85	3.94 _b
	Total	3.78	3.79	3.88	
Pleasantness	Yellow	4.99	4.89	5.51	5.13 _a
	Neutral	4.50	3.86	4.30	4.22 _a
	Violet	4.71	4.19	4.90	4.60 _a
	Total	4.73 _a	4.31 _{a,b}	4.90 _b	
Evaluation	Yellow	3.44	3.42	2.85	3.23 _a
	Neutral	3.81	4.38	3.63	3.93 _{a,b}
	Violet	3.52	4.01	3.50	3.67 _b
	Total	3.59 _a	3.94 _{a,b}	3.33 _b	
Spaciousness	Yellow	2.55	3.00	2.44	2.66 _a
	Neutral	2.94	3.16	2.92	3.01 _{a,b}
	Violet	2.69	2.73	2.73	2.72 _b
	Total	2.73	2.96	2.70	

Note: (1) For arousal and pleasantness higher scores indicate more positive assessments, for evaluation and spaciousness lower scores indicate more positive assessments. (2) Identical subscripts within a row or column indicate significantly different group contrasts ($p < .05$).

Assessment of evaluation

Again, the mean scores are reported in Table 2, but now higher scores represent less positive assessments. Lighting colour again rendered significant main effects, ($F(2,174)=10.58$, $p < .001$). Rooms with coloured light were rated more positively than the room with white lighting, but no differences occurred between the yellow and violet light. The main effect of Scent was also significant, ($F(2,85)=3.95$, $p=.02$), indicating more positive evaluations for the scented rooms than non-scented ones. The interaction between Lighting colour and Scent was not significant.

Assessment of spaciousness

Again, the mean scores are reported in Table 2, with higher scores representing less positive assessments (indicating less spaciousness). Also here, Lighting colour generated significant

main effects, ($F(2,174)=7.51, p=.001$). Rooms with coloured light were rated more positively than the room with white lighting. The main effect of Scent was not significant ($F(2,87)=1.11, p=.34$), nor was the interaction ($F(4,174)=1.50, p=.20$).

Discussion and Conclusions

The results reported in the literature showed that scents can influence the evaluation of a store environment. The study reported in this paper has demonstrated that scents can also influence the assessment of another type of environment, in this case a (hotel) bedroom. In general, the room was thought to be more pleasant and was evaluated more positively in both scented conditions than in the unscented condition. The kind of scent that was used in the room did not influence participants' evaluation. However, the scent conditions failed to evoke clear differences in arousal and spaciousness. Other studies using a similar scale for measuring pleasure and arousal also mostly found effects of scent on pleasure but failed to demonstrate effects on arousal (Mattila & Wirtz, 2001; Knasko, 1992; Fiore et al; 2000).

More significant effects were found for lighting than for the scents. Consistent with the literature, this study demonstrated that lighting positively affected the assessment of an environment. More specifically, coloured lighting elicited more positive evaluations of the room than white lighting. However, the room with the yellow lighting was experienced as more pleasurable than the room with the violet lighting. As with the scents, the colours also failed to generate a clear difference in the association with arousal.

Surprisingly, both colours resulted in higher scores on arousal than white lighting, even though the violet lighting itself was associated with a relaxing, i.e. unarousing atmosphere in the pre-test. During the experiments some participants remarked that they were amazed by the experience they had in the violet lighting condition, because it made them feel very relaxed and sometimes even sleepy. These participants expressed this feeling on items of the arousal scale, which was actually intended to measure the opposite of feeling relaxed. Thus although subjects informally reported that the violet condition was much more relaxing than the other two lighting conditions, this was not reflected in the data.

The present experiment did not demonstrate congruency effects between lighting colour and scent. Although the yellow light and citrus scent were rated 'refreshing' and the violet light and musky scent were rated 'relaxing' in the pre-test, combinations of these did not result in

significant interaction effects for any of the four dependent variables. These findings contrast those of Mattila and Wirtz (2001), who reported congruence effects of music and scent on consumer experiences, but they are in accordance with Spangenberg, Crowley and Henderson (1996), Clifford (1985) and Hellema (1994), who all report positive effects of neutral or pleasant scents on evaluative assessments, irrespective of their appropriateness. We conclude that both coloured lighting and pleasant fragrances influence people's evaluative assessments and, in addition, that congruency between coloured light and scent is of minor importance: their effects are purely additive.

The present study focused on short-term effects of coloured lighting and scent on the assessment of an environment. In future studies it would be interesting to investigate whether these effects can be validated over longer periods of time. Such longitudinal studies are especially relevant for environments where people typically spend relatively large amounts of time, such as a hotel or bedroom. Berlyne (1970) argues that when stimuli are new, people engage in specific exploratory behaviour where the novelty of a stimulus is its dominant property. As a person becomes more familiar with the stimulus a diversified exploratory behaviour is employed in which other stimulus properties, such as arousal potential and (perceived) complexity become more important. This process is likely to affect the liking for a stimulus. Hence, certain presets of lighting and fragrance might become boring after a while. One possible solution is offered by dynamic lighting. Future studies might focus on the effects of dynamic lighting in combination with ambient scent. Congruency might come to play a significant part in the longer term since people might become more aware of the stimuli in the room and therefore will notice incongruence.

The present study aimed to investigate the effect of lighting and fragrances as well as the interplay of these different sensory modalities on the formation of evaluative judgements of environments. The study was performed in a quasi-naturalistic setting, allowing for experimental control, without affecting the ecological validity of these natural, everyday evaluative processes. At present, existing scientific literature on effects of fragrances on evaluations is scarce, and the potential of olfactory stimulation is yet to be explored. We argue that the present study illustrates both the feasibility and relevance of this type of research and that it clearly calls for more efforts in this domain, geared at discovering the psychological processes behind these effects as well as their potential to enhance our enjoyment of environments and places.

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